

pH Metric Study of Complexes of Some Metal Ions with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde-4-Phenyl-3-Thiosemicarbazone

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Complexes of 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazones of Naphthaldehyde with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and VO^{2+} have been studied pH metrically. The proton ligand stability constant is 1.413×10^{10} . Stability constants of metal complexes are determined by half integral, Olerup and Least square methods in 70% dioxane water media. All the metals form 1 : 2 complexes. The order of stability constant is $\text{VO}^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} \approx \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+}$.

LIGANDS such as thiosemicarbazones are studied to a limited extent pH metrically. Here 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone (ONPT) derivative is studied with metals like VO^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} . The formation constants for their metals were calculated by Calvin and Wilson pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants are determined in 70% aqueous dioxane medium.

Experimental

The ligand 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone was synthesized and crystallised to get analytically pure (m.p. 210)¹. The solution of ONPT was prepared in dioxane (BDH AnalaR grade) which was further purified by standard method of Vogel². Metal nitrates used were of AnalaR grade which were estimated by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods. A Phillips pH meter was used for pH measurements. pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions having pH 4.33 and 9.1 at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

All titrations were carried out in a 100 ml beaker kept in water thermostat maintained at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Thirty five to forty five readings were taken in each case. Each titration was repeated to get reproducible results. The metal ligand ratio was maintained 1 : 5. The titration curves are represented in Fig. 1.

Blank Titrations

A mixture of 2 ml of 0.1M HNO_3 , 5 ml of 1.0M KNO_3 , 35 ml dioxane, 8 ml of water (to make the total of 50 ml in all titrations) was titrated with 0.2M NaOH until the pH rises to about 12.

Ligand titrations

A mixture of 2 ml of 0.1M HNO_3 , 5 ml of 1.0M KNO_3 , 5 ml of 0.01M ligand solution in dioxane,

30 ml of dioxane+8 ml of water was titrated with 0.2M NaOH solution.

Fig. 1. Titration curves for ONPT systems

Metal titrations

A mixture of 2 ml of 0.1M HNO_3 +5 ml of KNO_3 +5 ml of 0.01M ligand+1 ml of 0.01M metal nitrate solution (in case of cobalt 0.5 ml solution was taken)+30 ml of dioxane+7 ml of water was titrated with 0.2M NaOH solution.

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Results and Discussion

The practical proton-ligand stability constant for the ligand was calculated with the help of $\bar{n}_A$ values at different B values (pH meter readings in 70% aqueous dioxane-medium). $\bar{n}_A$ is calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti³ as adopted by Jabalpurwala *et al.*⁴. Plot of $\log \bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A$ against B is done to obtain a best straight line. From this straight line the values of the practical stability constant was obtained using the relation

$$\log PK_1^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$$

The proton-ligand stability constant obtained is 1.413×10^{10} . For metal ligand stability constants $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by the method of Jabalpurwala *et al.*⁴. The values of $\bar{n}$ are plotted against pL. The formation curves are as given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand formation curves of metal chelates of ONPT.

The values of $\log K_1$ were calculated by half integral method. But for calculation of $\log K_2$ least square method⁵ in which $\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})HL}$ was plotted against $\frac{(\bar{n}-2)HL}{1-\bar{n}}$ and Olerup's⁶ method was also used as there was not much difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$.

The average stability constants are given in Table I.

For $\log K_1$, it is observed that stability constants are in the order $VO^{2+} > Cu^{2+} \approx Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$.

TABLE I

Metal	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log B_1$
Cu ²⁺	9.68	9.30	18.98
Co ²⁺	9.70	9.31	19.01
VO ²⁺	9.85	8.80	18.65
Ni ²⁺	9.25	8.50	17.75

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